

**FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR
HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS LIVING IN DISTANT PLACES IN PUBLIC
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DISTRICT II-F, DIVISION
OF ANTIPOLO CITY**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 32

Issue 4

Pages: 480-486

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3074

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14898085

Manuscript Accepted: 01-158-2025

Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places in Public Secondary Schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City

Michael Angelo V. Rivera*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in distant places in public secondary schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2017-2018. The study considered 150 selected junior high school students in three public secondary schools in the said district. It was revealed that time management, motivation, study habits and productivity often influence the academic performance of students living in distant places. Sex, monthly family income and sibling position are Significant on the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in distant places. On the other hand, parents' educational attainment is not significant. Student – respondents obtained an overall mean rating of 78.83 with a standard deviation of 7.07 interpreted Fairly Satisfactory as revealed by their average grades in the first grading period. Academic performance of students and the factors such as time management, motivation, study habits and productivity are significantly related to students' academic performance. It was concluded that the academic performance of pupils is significantly associated on the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of students living in distant places with respect to time management, motivation, study habits and productivity.

Keywords: *academic performance, distance place, junior high school*

Introduction

Education is highly valuable in a globalized knowledge society in which technological and social changes are rapid. In such a situation, education has an impact on people's employability and their inclusion in society. In so doing, learning could indicate the amount of knowledge derived in the classroom as the individual interacts with various things to be studied.

Clearly stated, all individuals of school age living anywhere shall benefit from the law in order to lead their life in the future as much as possible essential for life's growth. Measuring academic performance of students is challenging since student performance is product of socio-economic, psychological and environmental factors. For the last 20 years, education in the Philippines is growing as a profitable industry with prime objective of maximizing profit by delivering high quality education that produces well-educated, skilled, mannered students according to needs and requirements of the dynamically growing market.

Gone are the days when students used to walk miles to access school, thanks to the emergence of alternative means of transport like school buses and private cars. However, even with these developments, there are students who still trek long distances to school, perhaps, due to high transport fares. And as such, education experts have often highlighted why parents need to factor the distances their children cover daily to and from school, whether by car or on foot.

It has been said that student performance depends on different socio-economic, psychological, environmental factors. The findings of research studies focused that student performance is affected by different factors such as learning abilities because new paradigm about learning assumes that all students can and should learn at higher levels but it should not be considered as constraint because there are other factors like race, gender, sex that can affect student's performance. Some of the researchers even tried to explain the link between students' achievements, economic circumstances and the risk of becoming a drop-out that proved to be positive

Although the transition from one level to the next is traditionally perceived as a positive opportunity for personal development, all students face intellectual and social challenges. While most students can successfully manage the process of transition, there is still a substantial minority (up to 20%) who do not adapt very well and who fail to fulfill the academic and social requirements of university life. Underperformance resulting from not being able to make adjustments in learning and social contacts is an even more frequent outcome. When geographical distance is involved, changes in the physical environment and the break with previous social networks make the transition more complicated. Students whose affective bonds with their hometowns are disrupted and whose sources of safety and identity are threatened have to develop associations with the new place, resulting in a more daunting transition.

In the same vein, there are many students in public secondary schools in Antipolo City who live in distant places and takes hours of travel before reaching the school. Some of them hardly reach the school on time but the vast majority is late all the time. This situation motivated the researcher to conduct a study on the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in distant places.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in

distant places in public secondary schools in District II-F, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2017-2018. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. monthly family income;
 - 1.3. sibling position; and
 - 1.4. parents' educational attainment?
2. What is the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in distant places as perceived by themselves with respect to:
 - 2.1. time management;
 - 2.2. motivation;
 - 2.3. study habits; and
 - 2.4. productivity?
3. Is there a significant difference on the perception of the respondents on the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students living in distant places as perceived by themselves with respect to the cited aspects in terms of their profile?
4. What is the level of academic performance of the student-respondents as revealed in their average grades in the first grading period?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance and the perceived extent of the factors influencing their academic performance?

Literature Review

Sadia (2015), stated that academic performance is something students achieve at school, college or university in class, in a laboratory, library or field work. An academic performance such as graduating in one's class, sometimes a purely quantitative matter, while having the findings of lengthy, comprehensive research published by a recognized journal is also a notable academic performance. When students get admission in a university, they have no idea about studies requirement.

In addition, Briggs (2010) stated that student achievement is influenced by a number of factors. Adequate study time is not enough to attain high grades and achieve great things. The education system around the world is changing and the literacy and basic knowledge levels are decreasing. Kids still go to school but they seem to be learning a lot less than kids who attended schools decades ago. The level of education is changing and so are the factors that affect student achievement.

Likewise, Ramirez (2008) posited that the term achievement refers to the degree or level of success attained in some specific tasks, especially school performance. Hence, scholastic achievement bears the meaning "the attained ability to perform school tasks, which can be general or specific to a given subject matter", the standard of excellence may be task related (ex. degree of accuracy in the performed act) or in other words scholastic achievement is the performance of the pupil's accomplishment in a subject of study.

Moreover, Lepper (2014) claimed that student motivation naturally has to do with students' desire to participate in the learning process. But it also concerns the reasons or goals that underlie their involvement or noninvolvement in academic activities. Although students may be equally motivated to perform a task, the sources of their motivation may differ. A student who is intrinsically motivated undertakes an activity "for its own sake, for the enjoyment it provides, the learning it permits, or the feelings of accomplishment it evokes". An extrinsically motivated student performs in order to obtain some reward or avoid some punishment external to the activity itself, such as grades, stickers, or teacher approval.

Meanwhile, according to Curva (2010), study skills are usually defined as student's ability to manage time and other resources to complete an academic task successfully. Study habit is the amount & kinds of studying routines which the students is used during a regular period of study occurred in a conducive learning. There are factors that would really affect the study habit of the child.

One study related to this paper is the study of Bernharu (2011) which was conducted to examine different factors influencing the academic performance of secondary school students in a metropolitan city of Pakistan. The results of the study revealed that socio-economic status (SES) and parents' education have a significant effect on students' overall academic achievement as well as achievement in the subjects of Mathematics and English. The high and average socio-economic level affects the performance more than the lower level. It is very interesting that parents' education means more than their occupation in relation to their children's academic performance at school.

In a similar vein, Alos (2012) determined the factors affecting the academic performance of fourth year student nurses. The factors affecting a student's academic performance arise from several reasons. Based from the findings, it was concluded that several factors pose a high impact on the academic performance of student nurses, with teacher-related factors topping the list. Among the five (5) domains, study habits and school-related factors fall behind the teacher-related factors. Nonetheless, both categories are still deemed to be highly impactful. Conversely, personal conditions and home-related factors pose little effect on student nurses' academic

performance.

Furthermore, Discutido (2009) conducted a study to determine the factors affecting the academic performance of Grade V pupils. The study concluded that Grade five pupils had near mastery of the competencies in English, Math and Science. Pupil factor, teacher factor and school factor are determinants of pupils' academic performance. Teachers and pupils had different perceptions with respect to parents' participation, exposure to media and pupil services.

Methodology

Research Design

The study applied the descriptive method of research utilizing a questionnaire-checklist as instrument of the study to gather the needed data. According to Vizcarra (2010), descriptive research is designed to study what is. It aimed to find out what prevail in the present conditions, relationships, opinions, processes and effects and developing trend.

Specifically, the study employed the descriptive survey research design utilizing a questionnaire-checklist as a tool in gathering data. Descriptive survey is a problem-solving approach which seeks to answer questions to real fact relating to existing conditions. This is a technique of quantitative description which determines the prevailing conditions in a group of cases chosen for study.

Respondents

The study considered 150 selected junior high school students in three public secondary schools in the said district as respondents of the study. They were identified as students living in distant places from their schools. They were described in terms of sex, monthly family income, sibling position and parents' educational attainment.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire-checklist was used as the main instrument in this study. To observe unity in the instrument, each aspect of the main problem was composed of statements which are closed-ended in nature. Further, the instrument was composed of two parts. The first part was made up of respondents' personal profile which included sex, monthly family income, sibling position and parents' educational attainment. The second part focused on the main problem of the research which is the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of students living in distant places with respect to time management, motivation, study habits, and productivity.

Procedure

The study followed the Gantt Chart of Activities in the conduct of the study. This includes the formulation of research problem up to the revision of the manuscript and submission of the final copy. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent. After the validation of the instrument, the questionnaire-checklist was administered to the respondents.

After the retrieval, the data were encoded and processed. Data processing and analysis were done. Based on the interpreted data, summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations were formulated. After the oral defense, the manuscript was revised considering the comments and suggestions of the Oral Examination Committee. After finalization, hard bound copies were submitted to the office of the Graduate Studies Program and other offices.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

The Profile of the Student-Respondents

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Student-Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Male	70	47
Female	80	53
Total	150	100
<i>Monthly Family Income</i>		
₱20,000 and above	24	15
₱15,000 - ₱19,999	28	19
₱10,000 - ₱14,999	64	43
Below ₱10,000	34	23
Total	150	100
<i>Sibling Position</i>		
First	13	9
Second	20	13

Third	40	27		
Fourth	39	26		
Fifth	29	19		
Sixth	9	6		
Total	150	100		
Parents' Educational Attainment	Father	Mother		
	f	%	f	%
College Graduate	38	25	32	21
College Undergraduate	35	23	40	27
High School Graduate	36	24	37	25
High School Undergraduate	30	20	27	18
Elementary Graduate	12	8	14	9
Total	150	100	150	100

As reflected in the table, in terms of sex, most of the respondents are females with 80 or 53 percent out of 150 students. In terms of monthly family income, most of the respondents belong to low-income families with 64 or 43 percent for income bracket ₱10,000 - ₱14,999 and 34 or 23 percent belonging to families with monthly income below ₱10,000. As to their sibling position, most of the respondents are either first, second and third child in the family. With regard to their parents' educational attainment, most of the parents have not finished their college education.

Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves

Table 2. *Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Time Management*

<i>Time Management</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I allot time for making my assignment.	3.87	Often
2.	I understand that there should be time to study my lessons.	3.25	Sometimes
3.	I clear all the boundaries of the lesson for review before I start.	3.62	Often
4.	I am eager to learn so I go to school early every day.	3.69	Often
5.	I answer assignments first before going to further research of some topics.	3.67	Often
6.	I allot time travel in going to school so I don't come late.	3.54	Often
7.	I do activities following the steps given by the teacher and submit it on time.	3.59	Often
8.	I was never late in submitting projects.	3.47	Sometimes
9.	I go home on time after class hours.	3.46	Sometimes
10.	I never skip class even though my house is far.	3.49	Sometimes
Overall WX		3.57	Often

The table reflects that with respect to time management, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.57 interpreted Often. First in rank among the items is "I allot time for making my assignment" with a weighted mean of 3.87 interpreted Often. Five other items are interpreted Often while four items are interpreted Sometimes. Last in rank is the item "I understand that there should be time to study my lessons" with a weighted mean of 3.25.

Findings indicate that students living in distant places try to manage their time in studying. This implies that there are times that students fail to submit requirements on time due to their distance from school. This relates to the statements of Curva (2010), that study skills are usually defined as student's ability to manage time and other resources to complete an academic task successfully. Study habit is the amount and kind of studying routines which the students is used during a regular period of study occurred in a conducive learning.

Table 3. *Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Motivation*

<i>Motivation</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I perform well in school because I want to have stable job in the future.	3.99	Often
2.	I enjoy studying alone without anybody disturbing me.	3.68	Often
3.	I participate actively and confidently because I am sure of my ideas.	3.97	Often
4.	I feel that education will help in my future plans.	3.94	Often
5.	I began to realize that finishing studies is possible.	3.92	Often
6.	I am interested in reading and writing just the way professionals do.	3.89	Often
7.	I know that studying alone would improve myself in terms of knowledge I would gain.	3.85	Often
8.	I am used to relying on my own ways of doing research work.	3.79	Often
9.	I am inspired to work alone without the help of my parents and other members of the family.	3.64	Often
10.	I only ask questions to my parents if I feel there is a need to.	3.72	Often
Overall WX		3.84	Often

As shown in the table, with respect to motivation, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.84 with all items interpreted Often. First in rank is "I perform well in school because I want to have stable job in the future" with a weighted mean of 3.99. Last in rank is "I am

inspired to work alone without the help of my parents and other members of the family” with a weighted mean of 3.64.

Findings reveal that students living in distant places are often motivated to enhance their academic performance. This implies that students living in distant places do their best to enhance their academic performance despite the hindrance of living in distant places. This relates to the ideas of Lepper (2014) that student motivation naturally has to do with students' desire to participate in the learning process. But it also concerns the reasons or goals that underlie their involvement or noninvolvement in academic activities. Although students may be equally motivated to perform a task, the sources of their motivation may differ.

Table 4. Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Study Habits

<i>Study Habits</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I enjoy working on my assignment as part of my routine.	4.25	Often
2.	I see to it that I am done with school work before watching TV.	4.29	Often
3.	I do my best to answer my assignment without asking help from my parents /brother/sister.	4.28	Often
4.	I gain more knowledge through studying alone.	4.02	Often
5.	I am used to studying alone after a short rest from school.	3.83	Often
6.	I show interest in studying before playing with some gadgets.	3.64	Often
7.	I perform better when I am prepared and has done everything at home.	3.04	Sometimes
8.	I discuss new ideas gained from research while doing independent study.	3.23	Sometimes
9.	I like to be used to studying lessons after school so that it would form part of my behavior.	3.61	Often
10.	I am used to studying lesson before going to bed.	3.76	Often
Overall WX		3.80	Often

As depicted from the table, with respect to study habits, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.80 interpreted Often. First and second in ranks are “I see to it that I am done with school work before watching” and “I do my best to answer my assignment without asking help from my parents /brother/sister” with weighted means of 4.29 and 4.28 respectively both interpreted Often. Six other items are all interpreted Often. Two items are interpreted Sometimes with last in rank is “I perform better when I am prepared and has done everything at home” with a weighted mean of 3.04.

The data reveal that students living in distant places have different styles of study habits. This implies that students believe that if they will have positive study habits, they will achieve better academic performance. This is in connection with the statements of James (2007) that quality education depends on the effective teaching, learning process, therefore, study habits is important factors that will be needed to upgrade the academic performance of the students. Quality of education is reflected through academic achievement which is a function of study habits and study attitude of the students. Thus, to enhance the quality of education, it is necessary to improve the study habits and study attitudes of the students.

Table 5. Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves with Respect to Productivity

<i>Productivity</i>		<i>WX</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	I finish my homework early when doing it alone.	3.87	Often
2.	I feel challenged in doing activities by myself.	3.50	Often
3.	I perform well when asked to work on a problem.	3.82	Often
4.	I am interested in learning when all the materials are available.	3.70	Often
5.	I learn a lot when I am alone without any disturbance.	3.77	Often
6.	I finish all homework and make advance readings of the lesson when doing it alone.	3.74	Often
7.	I learn how to manage my time when applying independent study technique.	3.84	Often
8.	I usually finish early and watch TV when doing my obligations on time.	3.53	Often
9.	I can still help my younger siblings after doing my assignment.	3.61	Often
10.	I offer help to my parents on household chores after doing my homework.	3.72	Often
Overall WX		3.71	Often

As depicted from the table, with respect to productivity, all items are interpreted Often with an overall weighted mean of 3.71. First in rank is “I finish my homework early when doing it alone” with a weighted mean of 3.87 while last in rank is “I feel challenged in doing activities by myself” with a weighted mean of 3.50. The data reveal that students living in distant places often accomplish the task assigned to them which shows their productivity. This implies that the respondents try their best to be productive students to achieve better performance. This is aligned to the statements of Suarez (2010), that being organized is key to becoming a productive student. By being organized, one can avoid losing homework, missing assignments and forgetting about tests. Productive students use effective productivity tools. Productive students also know what tools work best for students. Productive students have a plan.

Significant Difference on the Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves in Terms of Their Profile

As reflected from the table, with respect to all aspects, in terms of sex, monthly family income and sibling position, all the probability values are less than .05. This rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the extent of the factors influencing

the academic performance of junior high school students as perceived by themselves in terms of sex, monthly family income and sibling position. On the other hand, in terms of parents' educational attainment, the null hypothesis is accepted having p-values greater than .05 in all aspects.

Table 6. *Computed F-Values on the Significant Difference on the Extent of the Factors Influencing the Academic Performance of Junior High School Students Living in Distant Places as Perceived by Themselves in Terms of Their Profile*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>F_{comp}</i>	<i>p-values</i>	<i>H₀</i>	<i>VI</i>
Time Management	2.78	.006	Rejected	Significant
Motivation	4.65	.002	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	4.06	.008	Rejected	Significant
Productivity	4.97	.007	Rejected	Significant
<i>Monthly Family Income</i>				
Time Management	4.88	.049	Rejected	Significant
Motivation	4.94	.025	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	3.99	.034	Rejected	Significant
Productivity	4.89	.008	Rejected	Significant
<i>Sibling Position</i>				
Time Management	4.65	.006	Rejected	Significant
Motivation	4.88	.004	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	4.95	.009	Rejected	Significant
Productivity	4.77	.005	Rejected	Significant
<i>Fathers' Educational Attainment</i>				
Time Management	1.76	.787	Accepted	Not Significant
Motivation	1.46	.656	Accepted	Not Significant
Study Habits	1.44	.776	Accepted	Not Significant
Productivity	.94	.987	Accepted	Not Significant
<i>Mothers' Educational Attainment</i>				
Time Management	.99	.988	Accepted	Not Significant
Motivation	.84	.084	Accepted	Not Significant
Study Habits	.97	.078	Accepted	Not Significant
Productivity	.89	.922	Accepted	Not Significant

Findings indicate that sex, monthly family income and sibling position are significant on the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students. Findings imply that parents' educational attainment is not significant on the pupils' perception on the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students. This is similar with the findings of Dela Cruz (2014) which revealed that sex, monthly family income is significant on the perception of the pupil respondents on the determinants of academic performance in Mathematics.

Level of Academic Performance of the Student-Respondents as Revealed by their Average Grades

Table 7. *Level of Academic Performance of the Student-Respondents as Revealed by their Average Grades*

<i>Numerical Ratings</i>	<i>Descriptive Ratings</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
85-89 %	Very Satisfactory	15	10
80-84 %	Satisfactory	50	33
75-79 %	Fairly Satisfactory	60	40
Below 75 %	Did not meet Expectations	25	17
Total		150	100

As reflected in the table, the students obtained a mean performance of 78.83 interpreted Fairly Satisfactory with a standard deviation of 7.07. Out of 150 students, 60 or 40 percent have Fairly Satisfactory performance while 50 or 33 percent have Satisfactory performance. Meanwhile, 15 or 10 percent have Very Satisfactory performance, and the remaining 25 of 17 percent obtained did not meet expectations.

This means that many students need to study more to enhance their academic performance. This implies that students need to improve their study habits to attain better performance. This is in conformity with the statements of Sadia (2015), that academic performance is something students achieve at school, college or university in class, in a laboratory, library or field work. Some students, when entering the higher institution, feel free themselves from all the worries of studies which affect their studies negatively. Even they get failed in their tests or exams and there are some other poor study habits which affect the performance of the students.

Significant Relationship Between the Perceived Extent of the Factors and Students' Academic Performance

As depicted from the table, with respect to time management and motivation, the computed r-values obtained probability values less than .05. This rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of academic performance and the

perceived extent of the factors influencing their academic performance. Similarly, study habits and productivity are significantly related to students' academic performance since the *p*-values obtained are also less than .05.

Table 8. *Computed r-values on the Relationship Between the Perceived Extent of the Factors and Students' Academic Performance*

<i>Factors</i>	<i>r-values</i>	<i>p-values</i>	<i>Ho</i>	<i>VI</i>
Time Management	.94	.028	Rejected	Significant
Motivation	.86	.008	Rejected	Significant
Study Habits	.92	.015	Rejected	Significant
Productivity	.88	.009	Rejected	Significant

Findings reveal that academic performance of pupils is significantly associated with the factors influencing the academic performance of junior high school students. This implies that time management, motivation, study habits and productivity are contributory to the learning achievement of students. This is in connection with the discussions of Briggs (2010), that student achievement is influenced by a number of factors. Adequate study time is not enough to attain high grades and achieve great things. The education system around the world is changing and the literacy and basic knowledge levels are decreasing. Student achievement is often associated with the amount of study time they commit.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

Perceived extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of students living in distant places with respect to time management, motivation, study habits and productivity differ significantly when they are grouped according to sex, monthly family income and sibling position.

Academic performance of pupils is significantly associated on the extent of the factors influencing the academic performance of students living in distant places with respect to time management, motivation, study habits and productivity.

References

- Alos, S. (2012). *Factors Affecting the Academic Performance of the Student Nurses of BSU*. Benguet State University, La Trinidad, Benguet, Philippines.
- Bernharu, G. (2011). *Factors Affecting Students' Quality of Academic Performance: A Case of Secondary School Level*. Universiti Putra Malaysia, 2011.
- Briggs, R. (2010). *Student Learning Outcomes*. New York: MS Publishing Home Inc.
- Curva, L. (2010). *One Critique of the Research on Learning Styles*. Educational Leadership.
- Dela Cruz, M. (2014). *Determinants of Academic Performance in Mathematics of Grade Six Pupils*, Unpublished Masters' Thesis, Tomas Claudio Memorial College, Morong, Rizal.
- Discutido, M. (2014). *Academic Performance of Grade VI Pupils in Lunsad Elementary School, District of Binangonan II, Division of Rizal*, Unpublished Masters' Thesis, Tomas Claudio Memorial College, Morong, Rizal.
- James, W. & Gardner, D. (2007). *Learning Styles: Implications for Distance Learning*. New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education.
- Lepper, J. (2014). *Independent Study Techniques of Students*. American Journal of Education.
- Ramirez, D. (2008). *Study Habits of Students*. The Modern Teacher
- Sadia, B., (2015). *A Study of the Factors Affecting the Performance of the Students in Government Secondary Schools for Girls in Rawalpindi City*. Thesis, Faculty of Education, International Islamic University, Islamabad.
- Suarez, B. (2010). *Productivity of Students*, Educators' Journal, Vol X.
- Vizcarra, F. (2010). *Introduction to Educational Research*. Quezon City: Great Books, Trading.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Michael Angelo V. Rivera
Rizza National High School
Department of Education – Philippines